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CHRISTIAN A. DIAZ, DM-HRM
INSTRUCTOR III
Negros Oriental State University
diazxtian1984@gmail.com

“BECAUSE OF YOU, I AM FULL”

I walked through life with empty hands,
Searching far across the lands.
A soul once restless, torn and plain,
Till you came in, answered prayer.

Because of you, the nights are warm,
The storms have lost their fearful form.
Your voice, your touch, your silent grace,
Filled every cold and hollow space.

You gave me hope when mine had flew,
You turned the quiet words once drained.
Now bliss is fixed, deep and true,
Because of all I found in you.

No riches need I ever seek,
No worldly seat, no mountain peak.
For in your love, I've found it all,
Because of you, I am full.